

FLOODING IN NIGERIA: THE ACTIVITIES OF NEMA AND SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENTAL MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: *Flooding is the overflow of water overwhelming normal flow paths or patterns on its naturally defined course/channel with attendant effects on the environment and human population so located. Flooding has orchestrated population relocation, loss of livelihood, deaths, destruction of biodiversity and arable lands, destabilization of urban infrastructure, and other devastations after its occurrence. Addressing these resultant effects of flooding in Nigeria gave birth to the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) as an emergency response agency to provide necessary relief as first aid. The key functions of NEMA include formulating policies relating to disaster management, monitoring the state of preparedness against disaster challenges, and provision of relief materials to disaster victims in Nigeria amongst others. A cursory look at these functions vis-à-vis the activities of NEMA and ancillary disaster response departments has offered more worries than solutions; suggesting the need to ascertain the justification of NEMA's existence or otherwise. The findings reveal that in the absence of adequate control/prevention strategies, Nigeria succumbs to the damages of flooding, resorting to the disbursement of relief items as its main response, thereby relegating proactive control/preventive measures that are long-term solutions. The recommendation therefore, is to expand NEMA's statutory functions to accommodate physical developments aimed at minimizing flooding occurrences such as dams, embankments, channelization, and shoreline preservation amongst others; as against allowing it to occur perennially with the mindset being on the provision and distribution of relief materials to victims, which cannot assuage the dead and loss of properties. Hence, this paper proposed the expansion of NEMA functions and activities to accommodate prevention/control measures to create a new Agency called the National Emergency Management and Development Agency (NEMDA) for sustainable environmental management.*

Keywords: *Flooding, Disaster management, relief materials, NEMA.*

1.1 Introduction

Flooding can be referred to as water that is 'angry' having been frustrated on its natural flow path by accelerated human activities predicated on poorly regulated developments or nature reacting unusually

due to geographical elements and constraints. Globally, flooding is a very big issue even in developed countries but its disastrous effect is felt more by developing countries with overbearing economic, social, and political challenges made worse by primitive leadership corruption. Flooding has been with humans as old as the history of the earth. Biblically, we can recall or remember the flood of Noah that was orchestrated by God and wiped out the first human existence as captured in the book of Genesis in the Bible. Flooding is such a geological phenomenon that leaves a lot of disaster on its path and so should not be taken for granted as we seem to be doing in Nigeria and most countries globally. Mitigation efforts have become political with economic profiteering reflected by the setting up of 'trading bodies' that engage in relief materials business leaving citizens with unquantifiable losses. Rentschler, Salhab and Jafino (2022) study reveals recent disastrous floods in countries as diverse as Nigeria, Bangladesh, Vietnam, the United States, and the United Kingdom illustrating that the threat is a global reality. Njeru, (2023), states that East African countries suffering from devastating floods caused by climate change. Echendu, (2021) reveals that Ghana, a West African country with a population of 30 million people (approximately one-seventh the size of Nigeria) is plagued by perennial flooding with accompanying devastation, destruction, and deaths. Kimuli, Di, Zhang, Shaolin, Li, and Yin, (2021) stated that, while no single country is immune to the phenomena of climate change, the low-income countries (LICs) and Smallest Islands Developing States (SIDS) not only witness its consequences such as frequent floods, tropical storms and cyclones striking with a higher intensity as well as the prolonged drought but also suffer most from a number of their adverse effects. Matheswaran, Alahoon, Pandey and Amarnath (2019), attested that "floods cause catastrophic destruction to life and livelihood in South Asia than any other parts of the world, in that Floods affect more population than any other weather-related peril". In South Asian countries, floods affected more than 1 billion people in past 20 years (EMDAT, 2015). Rising populations, socio-economic development in flood prone areas and climate change will make 2 billion people vulnerable to flood disasters annually by 2050 (UNU 2004). Top 15 countries ranked on number of people affected by river flooding accounted for nearly 80 percent of the total population affected every year. Top flood prone countries lie in South Asia, where largest exposed population to flood risk currently resides (World Bank, 2015). For the past two decades, annual floods in Nigeria have resulted in the loss of 1,763 lives and damage to properties worth close to \$1 billion (Nura and Grey, 2022). The rise in water level may be caused by extreme precipitation or snow-melt affects the Asian block more than any other geographical location in the World. Flash floods occur through heavy rainfall or sudden release of water within a short period of time from dams such as Lagdo dam in Cameroon that has become a nightmare to Nigeria coastal settlements. Flooding is the most common and recurring disaster in Nigeria. The damage and losses recorded during the 2012 flood disaster were severe; however, the 2022 floods, which were on a multidimensional scale, had more devastating effects. Flooding has both natural and human consequences (NBS, NEMA and UNDP Report, 2023). It is perceived more as a common environmental

problem which connotes water overflowing its course. In their study on the menace of flooding in Nigeria, (Agbonkhese, Aka Joe-Abaya, Ocholi and Adekunle, 2014) describing “flooding as a menace and becoming a normal and re-occurring phenomenon which sometimes has devastating impacts on human livelihoods and infrastructural development; linking its occurrence to rapid population growth, poor governance, poor drainage facilities and decaying infrastructures, lack of proper environmental planning and management strategies, poor practice of dumping waste/refuse and climate change coupled with inadequate preparedness”. Mfom, Oguike, Eteng, and Etim, (2022), explains flooding as an environmental disaster that needs appropriate measures to be instituted to stem the tide of occurrence. They argued further that flooding is an extreme weather event naturally caused by rising global temperatures which result in down our, thermal expansion of the ocean and glacier melt which in turn result in sea level, thereby causing water to inundate coastal lands. However, flooding is a global natural hazard that has affected lives, led to the loss of properties and extinction of species in the environment. Umar and Grey, (2022) situates that flooding is experienced more in the Northern most part of Nigeria than the Southern part and hence management of flooding should be prioritised in the north with the expansive land mass and large population.

Reflectively, flooding is a threat that compromises the quality of the environment adversely. A cursory look at the issues relating to flooding, reveals it as a prerequisite for assessing environmental quality of human settlements. Hence, flooding is regarded as a regular global occurrence with far reaching mundane consequences. Due to the global nature of flooding and its relative negative implications, there have been numerous efforts by world governing bodies to intervene in the effects of flooding globally. For instance, the UNDP, The World Bank and such other notable bodies have intervened by providing affected areas with the necessary relief materials to cushion the effects so accelerated and disrupting livelihoods throughout the world especially in developing countries. It is in the developing countries that the problem is most severe due to poverty, corruption, inadequate infrastructural development, poor technological transfer, uncontrolled population growth, accelerated urbanisation and general poor environmental management options amongst others. Mfom et al (2022), isolated issues of weak management strategies and enforcement in relation to flooding occasioned by weak institutional and legislative framework in the development control process in developing countries. “For instance, developers build haphazardly without considering locations of flood plains and areas that are susceptible to flooding. There is also poor funding for relevant organizations to facilitate the creation of drainage distribution channels among other management options that can lead to the mitigation of flooding in the environment” (Mfom et al. 2022). In Nigeria, flooding has remained a prevalent environmental problem. Confirmed studies have revealed that there is alarming rate of occurrence of flooding (Ishaya et al., 2009. The studies pointed to the fact that flooding has negative implications on the survival of livelihoods, social and economic activities. Basically, in recent decades, flooding has led to the loss of thousands of lives and properties. Udoh, (2015) noted that flooding in

Nigeria is caused by weak implementation of planning policies, streams and channel obstruction due to indiscriminate waste disposal habits and human activities in flood plains. There is also the poor enforcement of development and planning regulations in Nigeria (Obru-Egboro, 2023)

Source: oasdom.com

History of flooding in Nigeria

Nigeria has had its own fair share of flooding like other climes over the years but notable occurrences are the only ones capture in history by regulating agencies. Flooding has become a major hazard in Nigeria in recent years. It is estimated that Nigeria suffered combine losses of more than \$16.9b in damaged properties, oil production, agriculture and other losses due to flood events in 2012 alone

(Echendu, 2021). Between the years 2011–2020, Nigeria recorded about 1,187 deaths connected to flooding, 15% of Africa’s deaths by flooding within the same period. The cost of damage to properties was \$904.5 million (Umar and Gray, 2022). Africa’s natural hazards include droughts, erosion, landslides, and flooding, because of the continent’s diverse climatic conditions. Recent studies have shown that flooding has been the most frequent and worst natural hazard in Africa within the last decade (Umar and Gray, 2022).

Oladokun and Proverbs, (2016) confirms that until recently major flood disasters rarely occur in Nigeria, but recorded cases of flooding in Nigeria date back to 1963 when Ogunpa River flooded Ibadan city causing loss of lives and properties with reoccurrences in 1978, 1980 and 2011 [Adegbola and Jolayemi (2012). The 1980 flood, which caused huge loss of lives and properties was a reminder of the disaster potential of the Ogunpa River.

Flooding has been the most frequent natural hazard in Africa in the last decade and Nigeria has been a major recipient of it. Langalla, UN Officer for disaster management said recently that since 1970 to date over 70million disaster has occurred in the continent and over 43 billion dollars expended on disaster interventions. She further isolated climate change as the major factor. Increasingly, a link is being made between increasing flood incidences and climate change (Echendu, 2021). In the last 50 years, Nigerians experienced two significant flood incidences in the years 2012 and 2018 precisely. In Nigeria, where flooding is common, data on its occurrence can be lacking at national, state and local levels and reports on flood events are usually incomplete ((Umar and Gray, 2022).

For instance, in 2012, Nigeria experienced its worst flooding in over 40 years, because of heavy rainfall across the country, for many days, and the Lagdo Dam in northern Cameroon east of Nigeria, used for electricity generation, and irrigation, releases its excess water. The 2012 Nigeria floods began in early July 2012. It killed 363 people and displaced over 2.1 million people as of 5 November 2012. According to the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA), 30 of Nigeria's 36 states were affected by the floods and the two most affected areas were Kogi and Benue States. The floods were termed as the worst in 40 years, and affected an estimated total of seven million people. The estimated damages and losses caused by the floods was N2.6 trillion.

Likewise in 2018, “the report released yesterday by the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) showed that as at October 9, 2018, a total of 103 Local Government Areas (LGAs) across 10 states in the country, were impacted by severe flooding with an estimated 1.9 million people affected. According to the report made available to THIS DAY Newspaper in Abuja by the agency, 561,442 people have been internally displaced while 351,236 are in need of immediate humanitarian assistance” (Sumaina,2018).

The year 2022 was recorded as a year of killings as published on page 15 of Saturday Vanguard (Nigerian Newspaper) of December 31st, 2022, highlighting the killing of 8, 058 persons orchestrated by Boko Haram, ISWAP, ethnic groups rivalry over land disputes and boundary issues, farmers and herders

skirmishes, security agencies killing civilians indiscriminately and devastating floods that swept across the country like 2012. In other words, 11 years after 2012 floods, the 2022 Nigeria floods displaced over 1.4 million people, killed over 603 people, and injured more than 2,400 persons. The Director, Planning, Research and Forecasting of the Agency Fatima Kasim disclosed during NEMA Emergency Coordination Forum held in Abuja affirmed that the 2023 floods affected the residents of 10 states and the following data has been collated in respect of 2023 flooding: Number of states affected – 10 states; Number of persons affected – 33,983; Number of persons displaced – 7,353; Number of persons injured – 75; Number of deaths – 5; Number of houses totally damaged – 1,679 and Farmlands totally damaged – 866 hectares. Further comprehensive information released by the National Emergency Management Agency, or NEMA, 33,983 people nationwide were impacted by the 2023 flood. A December 2023 report by the National Bureau of Statistics found that the disaster cost \$9 billion USD in economic damage.

The Nigeria Hydrological Science Agency predicted that in 2024, 31 states and 148 LGAs will be affected by floods. Reflectively, ten States were hit early by floods; Kaduna, Kano, Jigawa, Nasarawa, Taraba, Bauchi, Zamfara, Yobe, Sokoto and Kebbi. It is noteworthy to recall that these ten States account for over 50% of food produce in Nigeria every year. A devastating flood in 2024 killed 6, sacked 10,264 in the Madagali LGA of Adamawa reported on page 26 of Sunday Sun newspaper by Willy Graham Abel. Likewise, aggressive floods in the month of July, 2024 washed through hundred communities across Katsina State, displacing 25,000 people in 18 LGAs out of the 34 LGAs in the State. More than 7,000 houses destroyed, Sunday telegraph page 6. Same also in Jigawa State where 148 communities in 14 LGA are affected, while 2,744 hectares washed away in 12 LGAs displacing over 11, 500 households caused by torrential rainfall. As at September of 2024, floods has ravaged over 29 States out of the 36 States and Abuja affecting over a million people with more than 250 deaths (see plate 2). More severely affected was Borno State due to the overflow of water from the Alua Dam which precipitated damages to properties and loss of lives as has never been experienced in the history of the State according to the governor, Professor Babagana Zulum (see plate 1)

Plate 1: 2024 Flooding in Maiduguri, the Borno State capital.

Source: Joshua Olatunji/Dassociated Press

Plate 2: 2024 Flooding disaster outlook as at September

Source: NTA News Broadcast of 12th September, 2024

“Flooding occurs annually over most of Nigeria, but more frequently and with more impact in the northern states. This is attributed to a number of factors, including the bigger land-mass of the northern region, river paths, and the population of the northern region, which makes it both more susceptible to flooding and also more impacted by flooding. The states of Niger, Jigawa, Kano, and Yobe suffered more than five incidences of flooding over the 10-year study period, and Katsina and Kebbi each had five incidences” (Umar and Grey, 2021).

Flood is a major disaster in Nigeria

Number of persons displaced and affected by flood per state in thousands (2020)

Source: Stears, NEMA • Created with Datawrapper

Plate 3: An aerial view of houses submerged by flooding in the Anambra state of Nigeria.

Source: Nigerian National Emergency Management Agency

Causes and Effects of flooding

The causes and effects of flooding are numerous, varies and depends a lot on the geographical, ecological/geological characteristics and human interference in its occurrence. With the current global awareness of the concept of climate change, the causes and effects of flooding becomes reflective of climatic and meteorological variables. Hence, the Nigeria Hydrological Services Agency in its annual flood outlook situates the major causes of flooding in Nigeria as extreme weather conditions owing to climate change, soil condition and topography but not ruling out human activities in the blockade of water flow paths with solid waste and illegal land use developments. It has been established variously that one of the most prevalent natural disasters in Nigeria is perennial flooding due to complacency and ignorance of knowledge on the management of the nature of flooding. Adekola and Lamond, (2018) “The narratives of government, local communities and businesses align with the premise that flooding can and should be prevented whilst that of multilateral and business actors champion adaptation strategies on the basis that flooding is inevitable and hence more energy should be directed towards ‘living with water’—emergency response, damage reduction and the aftermath”. (Echendu, 2021), reveals that Nigeria’s flooding is mostly human induced and exacerbated by human-nature interactions, coupled with poor urban planning practices and inadequate environmental infrastructure being contributing factors. Her study cited these factors to include, poor and non-existent drainage systems,

poor waste management, unregulated urban expansion, poor implementation of planning laws, corruption that compromises policy implementation at all levels of administration and illegal developments along water channels or flow paths. For instance, the 2023 Nigeria floods was caused by climate change and heavy rain fall according to Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NIMET).

On the other hand the impacts of flood on the Nigerian population over the years have been enormous. In the absence of adequate prevention, Nigeria succumbs to the damage of these floods, resorting to the disbursement of relief items as its main response. This is because the attendant associated risks such as destruction of lives and properties, livelihood displacement, and impoverishment of victims arising from increasing flood cases have constituted a threat to the citizens’ survival and therefore inform the attention the menace has drawn among scholars, policy analyst (Okafor, 2020).

The annual flooding hazard causes more displacements than any other disaster though exact figures of perennial flood-related displacements, as well as deaths, are not certain from the available literature due to poor reporting (Cirella and Iyalomhe, 2018). The impact of flooding is felt more by the urban poor who tend to be the most vulnerable because they mostly live in marginal flood-prone locations with poor housing conditions that cannot withstand flooding (Echendu, 2021). The extent of flooding in Nigeria is so severe that it is a major limiting factor to achieving the SDGs (Echendu, 2020a). Effects and impacts of flooding fully illustrated by plates 3, 4 & 5.

The devastating effect of flooding in some selected locations in Nigeria

S/NO	STATE	DISASTER	ASSOCIATED HAZARD	NO OF PEOPLE AFFECTED	DATE & YEAR
1	Abia	Rainstorm	Houses	500	July 2001
2	Adamawa	Flood	Houses & Farmlands destroyed	500	April 2001
3	Akwa - Ibom	Flood & Rainstorm	367 houses washed away	4000	March 2001
4	Bauchi	Flood	750 Houses washed away, Farmlands destroyed	Not available	August 1988
5	Bayelsa	Flood	Houses, Schools, Markets & Farmlands submerged	2/3 of the population	1999 & March 2001
6	Borno	Flood	Houses & Farmlands	Not available	August 1988,

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Source: [semanticscholar.org](https://www.semanticscholar.org)

Plate 4: Flood victims relocating from their flooded homes to higher grounds

Source: Channelstv.com

Plate 5: A typical example of a flood affected street at Lagos, Nigeria

Source: Nation Newspaper

The place of NEMA in flood disaster

Mission and Vision of NEMA

Mission: To coordinate resources towards efficient and effective disaster prevention, preparation, mitigation and response in Nigeria.

Vision: To build a culture of preparedness, prevention, and response and community resilience to disaster in Nigeria (NEMA bulletin).

Addressing the resultant challenges of flooding in Nigeria gave birth to the establishment of the National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) as an emergency response agency to provide necessary reliefs. Therefore, NEMA a product of the establishment Act 12 of 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria as amended by Act 50 of 1999 is now vested with the statutory authority for managing all disasters including flooding in Nigeria. Notably also is the appointing of Federal Coordinating Officers (FCO) for disaster assistance at the State level in co-ordination with States Emergency Management Agency SEMA). NEMA in Nigeria plays a crucial role in disaster management and response. It is statutorily imperative for NEMA to effectively manage and mitigate the impacts of disasters in Nigeria.

Plate 6: NEMA Staff on their routine activity of disaster management

Source: thenationlineng.net

Here are some of its **key functions** and activities

- **Formulating Policies:** NEMA is responsible for creating policies related to disaster management in Nigeria
- **Coordination:** It coordinates plans and programs for efficient and effective disaster response at the national level
- **Monitoring Preparedness:** The agency monitors the state of preparedness of all relevant facilities and infrastructures
- **Relief Provision:** NEMA provides relief materials to victims of disasters to alleviate their suffering
- **Search and Rescue Operations:** It conducts search and rescue operations using various resources, including helicopters
- **Early Warning Systems:** The agency uses Geographic Information Systems (GIS) for early warning and precision in disaster response
- **Public Awareness:** NEMA conducts sensitization campaigns on disaster preparedness and waste management.

Gaps and challenges identified from data collation and consultations associated with NEMA

- Inadequate legal and institutional framework and advocacy;
- Poor engagement at the level of relevant institutions and the general public;
- Conflicting and unclear mandates of complimentary institutions;
- Limited understanding and information on environmental issues;
- Inadequate regulations in the area of land use planning and zoning regulation;
- Lack of baseline data as well as lack of access to relevant data for planning;
- Inadequate enforcement and collaboration;
- Lack of research and development; and
- Lack of adequate funding due to poor budgetary allocations.

Discussion of NEMA Functions and Activities

Echendu, (2021), argues that, historically, Nigeria has been more focused on post-disaster flood response than control. Reducing and addressing exposure to flood risk is now a national priority in the Nigerian government's disaster risk management agenda, but it is still motion without movement because not much has been achieved. Put differently, the Mission and Vision Statements of NEMA on the prevention of disasters in Nigeria are nothing but mere wistful thinking because nothing near prevention or control has been achieved in flood disasters in recent occurrences from 2012 to date. Before and during the events of flooding the response of NEMA is always in tandem with her statutory functions and activities centred principally on warnings, education, relocation of settlement population especially those located on lower grounds to upper lands, provision and distribution of relief materials

where necessary, amongst a host of other necessities as emergency response activities (see plates, 4 & 7). The statutory functions of the NEMA are well spelt out in the laws setting up the Agency and these functions appears inadequate since they are tailored towards tackling the issue of flooding on an ad hoc and short term basis which has not helped the devastations associated with flooding over the years because of the reoccurring nature of floods There is the need today to go all the hog for lasting long term solutions since peoples' lives and their possessions are severely affected with permanent reminders yearly of its occurrence. Emergency response only in the form of warnings, establishment of IDP Camps and relief material provision have become inadequate and unsustainable solutions in the management of the challenges of flooding that cannot be wished away through these approaches that have become riddled with corruption and misplaces priorities. The activities of NEMA have become a source of worry and apprehension to the inhabitants of Nigeria riparian settlements when the rainy season approaches or when dams are opened to let out excess water. With the severity of the nature of flood disasters now, due to climate change and human insatiable quest for technological development, there is the urgent need to overhaul the emergency management architecture to enable it deliver efficiency and realise its designed mandate. NEMA has focused more on waiting for the disaster to occur and offer remedies which cannot reverse permanent losses. More of control and preventive measures will ameliorate sufferings and also reduce the cost of mitigation when the rate of its happening is reduced to the barest minimum. Thus, minimising the occurrence of flooding offers better sustainable environmental management option in this era of climate change than the application of only emergency response efforts as presently practiced by NEMA and SEMA in the country. Today Nigeria is struggling to meet the United Nations SDGs on poverty, hunger and shelter partly due to improper management of flooding. Echendu, (2021), "the sustainable development goals are global goals for achieving environmental and human development by 2030. Of the 17 development goals, nine are directly affected by flooding. These include eradicating poverty and hunger as well as providing clean water and sanitation. In the case of Nigeria, flooding has had a major impact on the country's development goals in relation to the social, economic and environmental targets". In the NEMA mitigation response template on flooding, the emphasis yearly is more on the provision of relief materials for pecuniary gains (Oburu-Egboro, 2023).

Finally, the gaps and challenges identified from the field survey from interaction with NEMA officials reveals a situation that requires urgent redemption if Nigeria is really serious on tackling the problem of flooding in a holistic manner. For instance, in the area of funding, funds for emergencies are sometimes not released on time and in most cases insufficient to meet the extent of the devastation. It is interesting to note that 1% of Nigeria GDP and 20% of ecological fund are allocated to disaster management, but these funds are distributed among various Federal Ministries, including Environment, Health, States and LGAs and you can imagine in this line-up what percentage gets to NEMA. Specifically in 2023 the budgetary allocation to NEMA was 774million Naira. In like manner,

proposals for mitigation to forestall occurrences are hardly considered before the disaster reoccurs due to the bottleneck bureaucracies attributable to the unwieldy Nigerian civil service.

Plate 7: NEMA Officials distributing relief materials to flood victims

Source: Vanguardngr.com

Conclusion

With the coming of the philosophy of climate change, most natural disasters such as flooding have assumed frightening dimensions of devastation leaving graves on their trail in most countries, and Nigeria is not an exception. It is becoming more alarming and worrisome with the insincerity of developed countries to tackle the phenomenon of climate change. It is time to let the whole world know that no one is immune to the challenges associated with climate change. Commitment is key and we must re-order our values in terms of technological advancement and the hunger to surpass one another in terms of inventions. With all the noise or tangible concerns on climate change, some countries are still burning coal for their energy needs, thereby making all efforts to limit global warming to 1.5°C by the end of this century according to the United Nations-Paris Agreement, a mirage. Flooding will continue to harass us until we are ready to tackle it headlong through prevention/control techniques such as dams, embankments, channelization and shoreline preservation amongst others in addition to emergency response mitigation measures. Hence, the Nigerian experience is very worrisome in that we have become complacent, waiting for disasters such as flooding to occur, then the commencement of uncoordinated responses from NEMA follows because of inadequate planning, poor budgetary allocations and corruption. Complaints of flood victims, which are mostly ignored have always been in the area of inadequate welfare materials, poor location of IDP Camps, overcrowding, insufficient humanitarian staff, and general low response mechanism. All these were routinely experienced in the 2012, 2018, 2022, and 2024 floods in various parts of the country with identical frustrations and

devastations. A budgetary allocation of 774million Naira in 2023 as an example of poor funding is grossly inadequate to meet the internal spending of NEMA and the quantum of emergency response challenges thrown up by flood and other disasters in the country. Since NEMA is the Agency prepared statutorily for disaster response such as flooding emergencies, her activities should be properly funded and simultaneously expanded to include prevention/control techniques. Therefore, a new NEMA should be designed to incorporate the development of appropriate prevention/control strategies such as dams. This new Agency that will enable sustainable environmental management is now named NEMDA-National Emergency Management and Development Agency.

RECOMMENDATIONS

According to Professor Neal Hartman, “It is critical to shift thinking from achieving short-term goals to long-term objectives even while doing well in the short to medium term”. In other words, emergency responses are short-term efforts that should now support sustainable prevention strategies that are long-term for lasting solutions towards reducing the menace of flooding in Nigeria.

1. Amending the Law setting up the Agency to become more holistically proactive to provide emergency relief and control/prevention strategies to stop the disaster from re-occurring to engender sustainable environmental management. The addition of the ‘development’ strategy to its statutory functions will strengthen the NEMA's performance. The agency should now be known as the National Emergency Management and Development Agency (NEMDA) and State Emergency and Development Agency (SEMDA) at the State level for proper sustainable environmental management.
2. Expanding the functions of the agency to reinforce control/prevention strategies, has become sacrosanct because as an emergency response agency, it has gotten a lot of experience coupled with archived data on perennial flooding sites in the country especially those regions prone to flooding, and also being fully abreast of its causes and effects. Therefore, NEMDA and SEMDA are better positioned to tackle headlong the protracted menace of flooding by creating the necessary parameters concerning improved funding to prepare required prevention/control techniques such as dams, embankments, and levies along rivers and coastline prone to flood. Also, there is the need to include shoreline protection barriers, and dredging of the receptor rivers and streams in the flooding corridor of River Niger and River Benue which are more severely affected when the Lagdo dam in Cameroon releases excess water.
3. Assistance funding to the affected communities through a pooling of funds from establishments doing business in the area as a form of corporate social responsibility (as demonstrated by Dangote recently, donating 2 billion Naira to Borno State affected by 2024 floods) with the necessary government support in respect of tax waivers where necessary.
4. The agency should seek international exchange collaboration in the area of emergency response, modern prevention facilities development, smart technologies to tackle disasters when they occur and capacity building through training and continuous engagements with experts such as the United Nations Office for Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (UN-OCHA) and the United States Forest

Service, facilitated by USAID, and as was done recently at Abuja (Agbonkhese, Agbonkhese, Aka and Abaya, 2014).

5. Preparation of an environmental master plan as a working document to holistically tackle the menace of flooding and other environmental challenges. This instrument of planning will encompass a flood master plan that could act as a guiding document or requirement for sustainable environmental management concerning flooding.

6. Therefore, the statutory functions of NEMA in conjunction with the development of flood control/prevention strategies in the affected communities will institute long-term solutions especially, to assuage those who are victims of loss of lives, properties, and other valuables.

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